

Version	Date	Author name(s)	Description of Change
1	2025-22-05	M. Brandić Lipińska	First version

1 PROJECT SUMMARY VIDEO

The project video provided a comprehensive summary of the LUXWEX project, outlining its goals and developments.

The video was uploaded on YouTube and shared on a project website.

Link to the video on YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qoy-OPzX0pk>

Link to the video on project website: <https://luxwex.space/2025/01/19/luxwex-project-summary-video/>

1.1 Video content

The project summary video was professionally recorded [see Figure 1], and featured lab footage and interviews with some of the team members offering personal insights into their contributions [see Figure 2].

It combined professionally recorded project narration, providing the project rationale and an overview of the developed technologies, along with snippets from interviews with team members.

Figure 1. Video recording.

Figure 2. Screenshots from the video footage – Interviews with team members and system overview.

The video also provided project introduction and background and motivation [see Figure 3], an overview of the project partners [see Figure 4].

Figure 3. Screenshots from the summary video - Introduction, project background.

Figure 4. Screenshots from the summary video – Partner’s overview.

Animations were used to illustrate the mechanism behind the developed technology [see Figure 5]. The animations were instrumental in explaining the system’s functionality and the interaction between its components to extract and purify lunar water. This process was shown in the context of its application for in-situ propellant and consumables production, supporting future space exploration missions.

Figure 5. Screenshots from the summary video – Animation with a system overview.

The video concluded with credits listing all team members, acknowledging their contributions to the project’s success [see Figure 6].

Figure 6. Screenshots from the summary video – Credits.